

Information, Special Relativity and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Part 3

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 3, 2024

In this note we wish to clarify some points made in Parts 1 and 2. In an earlier note, we suggested that a rest mass (at rest) at a point x is proportional to an internal probability for a decay or some type of internal event to occur. In other words, a rest mass is linked with an internal clock. On average, time intervals between such internal events are proportional to $1/m_0$ so one may use $\hbar/m_0 c$ as clock intervals in the rest frame.

From special relativity, one has a Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$. In the rest frame $p=0$ and $E=m_0 c^2$. For x not approaching infinite, $A_1 = -m_0 c^2 t_1$, $A_2 = -m_0 c^2 t_2$... as the values of $A(i)$ at different clock gradation points. At first glance, one might consider the system seen in a frame moving at constant velocity, $-v$, in the following way. In such a frame, one has p' , E' , x' , t' such that $x'/t' = v$ and $A = -E't' + p'x'$. The question is then: What are the internal time gradations in such a frame? If one assumes that E' now takes the place of $m_0 c^2$ (because for $v \ll c$, $E \approx m_0 c^2$) one might suggest that one has time gradations of \hbar/E' , i.e. $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E'$. Then, because $x'/t' = v$, one would have $x = x_0 + n \cdot v \cdot \hbar/E'$ as corresponding spatial gradations. Such a view is based on Newtonian dynamics.

The problem with this viewpoint is that it does not preserve the Lorentz transformation, i.e. does not respect special relativity. E' follows from a transformation of $m_0 c^2$. One has a corresponding transformation of $p=0$ to p' . We suggest that one must examine $p=0$ in the rest frame. In such a frame, all x, t (fixed t) yield the same A , so there is the same probability for all x . Thus, one deals with probability in x and not dynamics in x .

As $x \rightarrow \infty$, $p \rightarrow 1$ so $A = -m_0 c^2 / m_0 c^2 + px$ (with $p \rightarrow 1$) $= 0$, i.e. the value of A for a photon. This same analysis should be applied to a moving frame, we argue, to respect the Lorentz invariant. For p not equal to 0, however, \hbar/p is no longer infinite. In other words, one has a restricted length (wavelength) associated with a nonzero p . At first one might consider this to be a mathematical manipulation, but the 2-slit experiment shows that this restricted length manifests itself physically.

$A = -Et + px$ and an Internal Clock

We have argued in a previous note that for a rest mass, m_0 , at rest with no external clock or external interactions, there is still a sense of time. We argue that internal events (e.g. decay) may exist in m_0 and should be proportional to m_0 if one has no specific knowledge of the physics of such events. Then, $m_0 c^2$ is proportional to the probability for an internal event and $1/m_0 c^2$ is the average time spacing (interval) for such an internal clock.

If one considers the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$, then for $p=0$, x not infinite, one has:

$$A = -m_0 c^2 t \quad ((1))$$

One may note that (a) all x, t points for the fixed t have the same A value and (b) $A_1 = -m_0 c^2 t_1$, $A_2 = -m_0 c^2 t_2$ etc.

Moving Frame

If one views m_0 from a frame moving with constant $-v$, then one has E', p', x', t' such that $x'/t'=v$. One may ask: What are the internal clock intervals in such a frame? Given that $E' \approx m_0 c^2$ for $v \ll c$, one might suggest that the gradations should be \hbar/E' . In other words, one has:

$$t' = 0 + n \hbar / E' \text{ where } n = \text{integer } 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{The corresponding } x' \text{ points would then be: } x' = 0 + n v \hbar / E' \quad ((2))$$

((2)), however, is based on Newtonian dynamics and ignores the probabilistic situation of all x points having equal probability in the rest frame.

Furthermore, the problem with this approach is that E' follows from a Lorentz transformation of E , but one has p ($p=0$) in the rest frame, and it too transforms to p' . Thus, ((2)) completely ignores the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$, i.e. does not respect special relativity.

As argued in Part 2, one needs to consider the role of px in the rest frame as $x \rightarrow \text{infinite}$. For $p=0$ we suggest that:

$$px \rightarrow 1 \text{ for } p=0 \text{ and } x \rightarrow \text{infinite} \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{For such a case: } A = -m_0 c^2 / m_0 c^2 + px \rightarrow 0 \quad ((4))$$

$A=0$ ((4)) is the value for a photon.

We suggest that in a moving frame, one must also consider $A=0$ to respect the Lorentz invariant. Thus:

$$\text{Time interval} = \hbar / E' \text{ and spatial interval} = \hbar / p' \quad ((5))$$

This means that the spatial interval now no longer has anything to do with $x'/t'=v$. The spatial interval is not due to the trajectory of the particle. This idea is a departure from Newtonian (and even classical special relativistic) dynamics.

In the rest frame, all x points have the same probability and one may choose x points up to infinite, but such is not the case in the moving frame. For $p \neq 0$, one has a wavelength or finite length linked to uniform probability, namely \hbar/p' . This uniform probability is manifested in $p'x'$, but to create a full probability such that $P_1(p'_1)P_1(p'_2) = P_1(p'_1+p'_2)$ one must use $\exp(ipx)$ (so that the probability does not grow or shrink indefinitely).

As a result, one has a dichotomy for spatial analysis. On the one hand, there is the $x'/t'=v$, but on the other hand, there are resolution or probability regions in time and space given by \hbar/E' and \hbar/p' for a free particle (constant v).

From the point of view of $A = -m_0 c^2$ in the rest frame, all x, t (same t) represent the same A . If one takes a particular x_1, t in the rest frame, it becomes x'_1, t'_1 in the moving frame with A preserved, i.e. $A = -m_0 c^2$. Then, in the moving frame A has this same value for $t' = t'_1 + n\hbar/E'$ and $x' = x'_1 + n\hbar/p'$. These new x', t' points transform back to x, t points in the rest frame, but only to a subset such that if one were to choose x_2, t in the rest frame and create $x'_2 + n\hbar/p'$ and $t'_2 + n\hbar/E'$, one would have the same set of x', t' in the moving frame.

Physical Consequences

At first glance, one may question whether there is any physical relevance to respecting $A=0$, i.e. special relativity, i.e. to the creation of wavelength regions, \hbar/p' , in space. The 2-slit interference experiment and also one dimensional reflection-refraction (calculation of reflection-refraction probabilities) shows that these wavelength pockets and the associated $\exp(ipx)$ are physical. In other words, nature seems to respect special relativity and free particle quantum mechanics seems to follow from it.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that nature respects special relativity even in terms of spatial probability regions, which we argue does not seem completely obvious. In a rest frame, $A = -Et = px = -m_0 c^2$. Any x, t point yields the same A as long as t is the same. This suggests that any x has the same probability, i.e. is on the same footing. This is a probabilistic statement. We argue that $1/m_0 c$ is the average time interval for an internal event in m_0 in the rest frame. In other words, $m_0 c$ is proportional to the probability for an internal event.

In the moving frame, we suggest that \hbar/E' is the time interval. One might then suggest that a $t = t_0 + n\hbar/E'$ corresponds to an $x = x_0 + v * n\hbar/E'$ using $x'/t'=v$. In other words, Newtonian dynamics governs the x' position. This, we argue, does respect special relativity.

In the rest frame, one has A constant for all x, t . This statement is linked to $p_x \rightarrow 1$ for $p=0$ and $x \rightarrow \infty$. $x \rightarrow \infty$ means one may choose any x point (finite) with equal probability. Then: $A = -m_0 c^2 + p_x = 0$ (like the photon case) and this special relativistic invariant should be respected in other frames. This suggests that for $A = -E't' + p'x'$, one has $t = t_0 + n\hbar/E'$ and $x = x_0 + n\hbar/p'$. Thus, there is a spatial resolution not based on $x'/t' = v$, but rather one which respects the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$. This means one has a spatial region (wavelength) \hbar/p which is less than infinite (from the rest frame) case, in which there is equal x probability. This is described by the uniform probability $p'x'$. To have $P_1(p_1')P_1(p_2') = P_1(p_1'+p_2')$, however, one requires an shell function carrying $p'x'$ or $\exp(ip'x') = P_1$ so P_1 does not grow or shrink indefinitely in x . This then is directly associated with free particle quantum mechanics, we argue.

In other words, free particle mechanics arises from respecting the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ when considering uniform probabilities in x . The 2-slit experiment and others confirm the existence of the \hbar/p' length region.